

AI-EmpaTe

**EVALUATION
FRAMEWORK FOR
ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE
LITERACY**

Evaluation Framework for Artificial Intelligence Literacy

March 2025

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Executive Summary

This report presents an evaluation framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) literacy developed within the Erasmus+ AI-EmpaTe project. Drawing on a mixed-methods design, data were collected through an online survey completed by 1,035 pre-service and in-service teachers in Latvia, Israel, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia, complemented by eight focus groups with teacher educators and parents. Grounded in Tenberga and Daniela's (2024) six-component model, the framework examines AI literacy across understanding, critical evaluation, ethics, usage, awareness, and communication. The findings suggest that while teachers are becoming more confident in using generative AI (GenAI) tools, competencies related to critical evaluation, ethical reflection, and communication remain comparatively underdeveloped. Cross-country patterns further highlight the importance of context-sensitive approaches to AI literacy. The report concludes that AI literacy must extend beyond technical proficiency by embedding ethical, social, and pedagogical dimensions in teacher education and professional development to support equitable, human-centred education

About the Project

Project Title: AI-Empowered Teaching: Unlocking the Future of Digital Education for Teachers (AI-EmpaTe)

Project Code: 2024-1-LV01-KA220-HED-000250857

Project Summary

AI-EmpaTe, an Erasmus+ KA220-HED project, aims to equip pre-service teachers and in-service teachers in primary and secondary education with the fundamental knowledge, skills, and competences needed to integrate AI as teaching content in education. The project will develop an open online course to support pre-service and in-service teachers in planning, preparing, and implementing AI-supported instructional practices.

Key Objectives

- Develop AI literacy among pre-service and in-service teachers
- Design an Open Online Course for AI in education.
- Create a handbook on best AI teaching practices.
- Pilot an AI education framework with pre-service and in-service teachers.
- Provide policy recommendations for ethical AI integration.

Core Activities

- **Handbook on AI Best Practices Volume I:** A reference guide for policymakers, researchers, educators, and other stakeholders involved in the integration of AI in education.
- **Handbook on AI Best Practices Volume II:** A practical guide for pre-service and in-service teachers on implementing AI in educational settings.
- **Open Online Course:** Covering AI concepts, integration strategies, ethics, and practical applications.
- **Pilot Testing:** Engaging 80 pre-service teachers and 80 in-service teachers.
- **Resource Development:** 8 video tutorials, an AI evaluation framework, and policy recommendations.

Broader Implications

- Dissemination through webinars, publications, and collaboration with policymakers.
- Strengthening cross-national university-school partnerships to bridge research, training, and practice.

Project Partners

- University of Latvia (Latvia)- Coordinator
- Tel Aviv University (Israel)
- Charles University (Czech Republic)
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1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly reshaping education, influencing how teachers plan, deliver, and evaluate instruction. Generative AI (GenAI) tools such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and Copilot are increasingly embedded in classrooms, teacher education, and everyday learning beyond school. While these tools may enhance efficiency and open new instructional possibilities, they also raise significant pedagogical and ethical concerns. Issues such as academic integrity, bias, privacy, and equity highlight that AI is not merely a technological development but a disruptive force in educational practice and decision-making.

In this context, the need for robust AI literacy is clear. Teachers, students, parents, and teacher educators must not only use AI, but also understand, evaluate, and communicate about it responsibly. This report develops an evaluation framework to assess these competencies. Building on Tenberga and Daniela's (2024) six-component model, it examines how the framework operates across different national contexts and highlights tensions between global frameworks and local realities.

2. Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018) to develop an AI literacy framework supporting both pre-service and in-service teachers in the educational use of GenAI. Data were collected via an online survey and focus group interviews, providing quantitative breadth and qualitative depth.

The survey was conducted between December 2024 and February 2025 in Israel, Latvia, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia. Using convenience sampling, the survey was distributed through professional and social networks and yielded responses from 473 pre-service teachers and 562 in-service teachers. The questionnaire comprised two sections. The first collected demographic information (e.g., gender, age, teaching experience, subject area, and current use of AI tools). The second included 25 Likert-scale items (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree) addressing familiarity with GenAI, classroom use, and attitudes toward pedagogical and ethical issues.

Three open-ended questions explored examples of successful use, challenges, and professional development needs. The instrument drew on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and was organised around five themes: lesson planning, teaching, assessment, ethical and responsible use, and professional development.

To complement the survey, focus groups were conducted in each country with teacher educators and parents. Group size varied slightly across countries due to recruitment and participant availability. In total, 23 parents (Israel n=10, Latvia n=5, Slovakia n=5, Czech Republic n=3) and 21 teacher educators (Israel n=5, Latvia n=5, Slovakia n=5, Czech Republic n=6) participated, representing a range of professional backgrounds and levels of digital competence. Focus groups were audio-recorded with consent, transcribed, and analysed thematically by national teams using shared guiding questions. Thematic coding supported both country-level interpretation and cross-country comparison, enriching and contextualising the survey findings.

Several AI literacy frameworks were reviewed to situate the study in established scholarship (e.g., Ng et al., 2021; Yue et al., 2025; Touretzky et al., 2023; UNESCO, 2024; OECD, 2025; Bekiaridis & Attwell, 2024). For this project, Tenberga and Daniela's (2024) six-component framework was adopted due to its relevance to educational practice and its integration of technical, ethical, communicative, and awareness dimensions. Each component was mapped to specific survey items (Table 1).

Table 1. AI Literacy Components, Definitions, and Corresponding Survey Items

Component	Focus	Questionnaire items
Understanding	Basic AI concepts and how they work	Q3, Q6, Q13
Critical evaluation	Analysing outputs, identifying bias and limitations	Q4, Q9, Q12, Q14
Ethics	Awareness of privacy, fairness, and accountability	Q18, Q19, Q20
Usage	Practical application of AI tools in teaching	Q1, Q2, Q7, Q8, Q11, Q15, Q17
Awareness	Broader social, cultural, and educational implications	Q5, Q10, Q21, Q22, Q23, Q25
Communication	Ability to explain and discuss AI	Q16, Q24

In addition, qualitative responses to the open-ended questions (Q26–Q28) were analysed thematically and aligned with the six components. By integrating these data sources within a context-specific framework, the study provides a foundation for evaluating AI literacy and identifying the competencies and support structures teachers need to use GenAI effectively and responsibly.

3. Evaluation Framework: Strengths and Gaps

The six-component framework offers a structured approach to assessing AI literacy. By incorporating technical, ethical, and communicative dimensions, it avoids the narrow emphasis on technical competence found in some earlier models (Ng et al., 2021). At the same time, applying the framework also reveals limitations that reflect broader tensions in AI and education research.

Understanding

Teachers generally reported familiarity with GenAI tools, but a limited grasp of how AI systems function. This echoes a recurring challenge in AI literacy research: distinguishing between functional knowledge (knowing how to use tools) and conceptual literacy (understanding how they work) (Long & Magerko, 2020; Ng et al., 2021). As a result, the framework risks conflating tool proficiency with deeper epistemic understanding of AI. Without such critical grounding, teachers may remain positioned primarily as consumers of technology rather than informed professionals able to question its design, assumptions, and purposes (Selwyn, 2019).

Critical Evaluation

While participants could identify obvious factual inaccuracies in AI outputs, they struggled to interrogate subtler issues such as algorithmic bias, embedded cultural assumptions, and hidden commercial logics. This aligns with Knox's (2020) argument that educational uses of AI can obscure the ideological values encoded in data and algorithms. Although the framework captures practices such as "checking outputs," it may not sufficiently prompt teachers to examine the systemic forces shaping those outputs. As Holmes et al. (2022) note, AI in education is not merely a technical tool but a socio-technical system, and critical evaluation must extend beyond surface-level accuracy.

Ethics

Ethical concerns were among the most prominent themes, particularly regarding plagiarism and student misuse. However, this emphasis risks narrowing ethics to classroom-level misconduct while overlooking structural issues such as surveillance capitalism, data extraction, and unequal access (Williamson & Eynon, 2020; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). When ethics is framed primarily through academic integrity, the framework may underrepresent the broader political economy of AI in education.

Usage

Teachers frequently reported using GenAI for lesson planning, quiz generation, and feedback. Yet these applications often reflected instrumental efficiency rather than pedagogical depth. As Knox (2020) and Selwyn (2019) argue, such uses can reduce teaching to technical administration and shift creative or intellectual labour toward automated systems. The framework captures usage, but it may inadvertently equate frequency of use with meaningful pedagogical integration.

Awareness

Awareness of AI's wider societal implications appeared underdeveloped. Teachers often viewed AI as a neutral classroom aid rather than a technology reshaping labour markets, governance, and cultural life. This reflects what Williamson (2022) describes as the "black-boxing" of AI, where broader social and political implications are eclipsed by classroom narratives of efficiency and personalisation. Without more explicit attention to power, inequality, and global governance debates, the framework risks reinforcing a narrow, instrumental view of AI literacy.

Communication

Communication emerged as the weakest area. Both teachers and parents struggled to explain AI in accessible terms or engage in informed dialogue with others. This gap reflects not only limited individual skill but also the absence of a shared public discourse around AI (UNESCO, 2024). If educators cannot articulate what AI is and what it implies for learning, they are less able to mediate between technological systems and students' understanding. While the framework identifies this gap, it provides limited guidance on how to cultivate communication and dialogue as a core dimension of AI literacy.

4. Key Findings

- Pre-service teachers reported high enthusiasm for GenAI adoption but often showed limited critical depth, aligning with research suggesting that early-career educators may be confident users while still developing skills for evaluating risks (Zhong & Liu, 2025).
- In-service teachers tended to be more cautious and pragmatic; however, their awareness of risks did not consistently translate into concrete pedagogical strategies, reflecting tensions between professional responsibility and institutional pressures for innovation (Sperling et al., 2024).

- Parents frequently expressed ethical concerns but also reported limited technical knowledge, echoing UNESCO's (2024) warning that families are often marginalised in AI literacy initiatives.
- Teacher educators demonstrated broader awareness but reported difficulties modelling classroom integration, underscoring the persistent gap between policy frameworks and the realities of teacher education (Holmes et al., 2021).

Cross-country patterns reinforced that AI literacy is context-dependent. In the present sample, Latvia and the Czech Republic showed comparatively stronger emphasis on ethical considerations, Israel reflected greater concern with uncertainty and risk, and Slovakia demonstrated relatively stronger critical evaluation. These findings support OECD's (2025) argument that AI competencies should be adapted to national and cultural contexts rather than implemented as universal standards.

Implications

1. Curriculum integration should avoid treating AI literacy as an add-on. Without embedding ethical, social, and communicative dimensions across curricula, teachers risk being positioned primarily as users rather than critical practitioners (Selwyn, 2019).
2. Professional development should move beyond technical training and cultivate reflective, critical engagement with AI, including attention to power, inequality, and systemic risks (Knox, 2020; Williamson, 2022).
3. Policy frameworks must remain realistic. Global guidelines such as those from OECD (2025) and UNESCO (2024) are aspirational, but many schools lack the resources, support, and professional learning needed for effective implementation.
4. Parent engagement should be central. Parents are often the first to observe children's use of AI yet remain peripheral in many initiatives; they need targeted resources to navigate both opportunities and risks.
5. Assessment should avoid checklist approaches to AI literacy. Scenario-based, reflective, and dialogic assessments are better suited to capturing critical and ethical competencies (Ng et al., 2021).

5. Conclusion

Tenberga and Daniela's (2024) six-component framework provides a valuable structure for assessing AI literacy, particularly because it extends beyond technical skills to include ethics, awareness, and communication. However, its application also reveals limitations: the framework risks remaining descriptive rather than transformative if it does not engage more directly with systemic forces such as commercialisation, inequality, and the governance of AI in education.

Overall, the findings indicate that while teachers are increasingly confident in using AI tools, their capacity to critically question, ethically integrate, and communicate about AI remains uneven. Pre-service teachers require stronger grounding in critical evaluation; in-service teachers need support in translating awareness into practice; and parents need accessible entry points. Teacher educators face the additional challenge of aligning global frameworks with local classroom realities.

Ultimately, evaluating AI literacy is not only about measuring competencies but also about strengthening critical reflection and responsible educational practice. Without this, AI integration risks reproducing existing inequalities and narrowing education to technical management rather than supporting human-centred, democratic learning.

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8. Appendices

Appendix A

Survey for Pre-Service and In-Service Teachers

Teachers' Needs and Perspectives on GenAI in Teaching and Learning

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) refers to systems such as ChatGPT, Claude, Copilot, Gemini, Midjourney, and many others that generate new content like text, images, and code based on patterns learned from vast amounts of data.

This survey aims to assess teachers' needs and perspectives regarding the use of GenAI in educational settings. It touches on key areas such as preparation, in-class use, and feedback, as well as the importance of ethical use and capacity-building for teachers.

Thank you for taking the time to answer this questionnaire and participate in our research.

The questionnaire is anonymous and respondents cannot be identified. Your information will not be shared with anyone outside of the research team. Completing the questionnaire should take approximately 20 minutes.

There are no wrong answers, so please feel free to answer honestly!

Demographics

- Gender:
 - Male Female Other
- Age: _____
- Education:
 - Secondary education BA degree MA degree (teacher education)
 - MA degree (other) PhD degree
- Teacher Qualification: Yes No
- Years of teaching experience: _____
- Teaching subject:
 - Science Math Art & Music Social Studies Language Other: _____
- Level of education where I teach:
 - Primary Secondary Higher education Other: _____
- GenAI tools you used (select all that apply):
 - ChatGPT Copilot Claude Gemini MidJourney Other: _____

Part 1: Before Teaching

Focus: Preparation and GenAI Literacy

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

1. I feel confident in my ability to use GenAI tools to enhance my teaching practices.
2. I use GenAI tools to plan and design engaging lesson materials.
3. I feel confident in developing or customising GenAI-based tools for teaching.
4. I can evaluate the content generated by GenAI tools for accuracy and appropriateness.
5. I am familiar with the applications of GenAI in personalised and adaptive learning.
6. I understand how GenAI works (e.g. training on large datasets, machine learning).

Part 2: During Teaching

Focus: Enhancing Classroom Learning with GenAI Tools

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

7. I use GenAI to provide real-time support to students.
8. I find GenAI tools help students engage more actively.
9. I can explain to students how to critically assess GenAI-generated content.
10. I believe GenAI promotes creativity and problem-solving among students.
11. I encourage students to use GenAI for self-regulated learning and research.
12. I am concerned about students becoming overly dependent on GenAI tools.
13. I can explain to students how GenAI works and how it differs from other AI types.
14. I can distinguish between students' personal work and GenAI-generated work

Part 3: After Teaching

Focus: Assessment and Feedback

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

15. GenAI assists me in analysing students' performance and giving personalised feedback.
16. I find GenAI helps streamline my assessment process while maintaining standards.
17. I use GenAI insights to adapt future lessons and strategies.

Part 4: Ethical and Responsible Use

Focus: Understanding and Mitigating Risks

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

18. I am aware of the ethical challenges of GenAI and take steps to mitigate them.
19. I teach students about the ethical responsibilities involved in using GenAI.
20. I am aware of institutional guidelines or policies on GenAI use.
21. I believe it is important to teach students to create content with GenAI, not just consume it.

Part 5: Teacher Professional Development

Focus: Building Teachers' GenAI Competency

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

22. Teachers should have knowledge and skills to guide students in GenAI use.
23. I am interested in professional development on using GenAI effectively.
24. My institution provides sufficient support and resources for GenAI integration.
25. I have experienced challenges in integrating GenAI into the curriculum.

Part 6: Open-ended Questions (Open-ended Questions)

26. What successful uses of GenAI in your teaching have you experienced or planned?
27. What challenges or concerns do you face when using GenAI? Have you found solutions?
28. What types of professional development would help you feel more confident using GenAI?

Appendix B Focus Group Questions for Teacher Educators

Questions for focus groups with teacher educators were related to four topics:

Topic 1: Understanding (Gen)AI in Education//Experiences with GenAI

- Have you tried any tools using GenAI? (What specific tools or types of tools? In what situations or for what purposes? What fears or feelings did it leave in you?)
- Do you have any favorite GenAI tools?
- Do you use GenAI in your teaching? (What types or tools? What is the effectiveness or benefit?)

Topic 2: GenAI in Education

- What information do you have about using GenAI in education?
- Do you know any conceptual or complex solutions or specific use cases in this area?
- What is your opinion on the use of GenAI in teaching in general?
- What options and ways of involving GenAI in teaching can you think of? How do you feel about these options?
- Are you interested in whether the Ministry of Education, your university or other organisations (NPI, etc.) have issued or are issuing any guidelines for the use of GenAI in schools? (Are you aware of this?)

Topic 3: GenAI and teacher competency

- What knowledge, skills, and dispositions are essential for teachers to be able to use GenAI in teaching?
- What knowledge, skills, and dispositions are essential for teachers to navigate the evolving landscape of GenAI in education?

Topic 4: Supporting teachers' professional development

- Do you have any experience with training teachers or student teachers in the use of GenAI?
- Do you consider any (potential) issues or concerns related to the use of GenAI in teacher education?

Appendix C Focus Group Questions for Parents

Questions for focus groups with parents were focused on following four topics:

Topic 1: Understanding (Gen)AI in Education

- Have you tried any tools using GenAI?
- What specific tools or applications?
- In what situations or for what purposes?
- What concerns or feelings did it leave you with?
- Do you have any favorite GenAI tools?
- Are you positive (“enthusiastic”) or more concerned?
- Do you discuss AI issues with your children at home?
- Do you use AI with your children at home?

Topic 2: Gen-AI should used in schools

- How did you find out about it?
- Did the school/teachers hold any discussions with parents on this topic?)
- What do you think about the importance of GenAI for school results and skill development in children?
- Do you see it more positively or negatively?
- Will GenAI help or harm?
- Do you have any ideas about how teachers could or should use GenAI with children in their lessons?

Topic 3: GenAI in Curriculum and support

- Do you know whether the Ministry of Education or the Institution responsible for education in your country has issued or is issuing any guidelines for the use of GenAI in schools?
- Would you support the implementation of GenAI tools in the school curriculum?

Topic 4: Expectations/ The future of AI in Education

- What will be the future involvement of GenAI in the work of teachers?
- What will it look like with GenAI and education in general?
- What measures would you like to implement to ensure the responsible use of GenAI in education?